

THE EFFECT OF SPORT NOSTALGIA ON DISCRETE POSITIVE EMOTIONS, POSITIVE eWOM, AND REVISIT INTENTION OF SPORT TOURISTS: A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

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Abstract

Sport nostalgia has been identified as a key factor to understand sport tourists' revisit intention. This study is among the first to establish a conceptual model that links sport nostalgia, discrete positive emotions, positive electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), and revisit intention in the sport tourism context. The conceptual model is based on Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) model, because of its theoretical importance. As such, it is a rare attempt to explain the role of upbeat / elation, serenity / calm, warm / tender emotions, and positive eWOM in sport tourism research. This conceptual model will help to understand how sport tourists' revisit intention can be enhanced and will assist sport marketers and policy makers to establish appropriate marketing strategies related to sport nostalgia. Designing unique, tailor-made and, memorable experiences can increase sport nostalgia, and, particularly, discrete positive emotions, and positive eWOM, in the sport tourism context. A methodological approach is also suggested to empirically test the hypotheses proposed in the study.

Keywords: Sport Nostalgia, Positive Emotions, Positive eWOM, Revisit Intention, Sport Tourists.

1. INTRODUCTION

Academicians and practitioners have started considering sport tourism as a very important phenomenon over the past few decades (Malchrowicz-Mosko & Munsters, 2018). Sport tourism is considered to be one of the most profitable markets in tourism (Smith & Stevenson, 2009). Sport-related travel accounts for 15% to 30% of tourism earnings, and we can expect the numbers to increase (Vehmas, 2010). Because of sport tourism's impact on the economy, scholars are trying to better comprehend the reasons for individuals to participate in sporting events.

Sport leverages its popularity mainly because of sport fans and consumers. Travelling widely, dialing into sport websites, watching live television broadcasts, reading the sports pages of the newspapers are some of the activities sports fans and consumers engage in (Horne, 2006). National pride, escapism, and a sense of personal and collective identity are some of the cultural, social, and psychological needs that drive sport consumer experience. Many sport consumers travel long distances and often get involved with their consumption objects (Wann et al., 2001; Hughson, 1999).

Past emotional memories that are strong make people long for the good old days. In today's society, people think about the past and they want to return to simpler times that are less corrupt. They want to come out of their busy schedule in their lives (Chase & Shaw, 1989). Previous positive experiences motivate sport tourists to become emotionally attached to their favorite teams. A strong reason that motivates sport tourists to attend the home and away games is the nostalgic recollections of moments that they do not forget (Fairley, 2003).

Their rational passion of fans, limited availability, and sport-specific atmosphere are some of the unique characteristics of spectator sport (Hinch & Higham, 2001; Kelly, 1982). Cho et al. (2014) found that these characteristics affect the generation of nostalgia. They further added that different experiences in sport settings such as cheering for a player, memories of childhood, and socializing with others can elicit and are connected to nostalgia. They also asserted that nostalgia plays a significant role in comprehending the behaviour of sport tourists and consumers. Small-scale and large-scale events attract not only local fans but also outside fans (Kaplanidou & Vogt, 2007).

Multiple types of stimuli affect sport tourists as they often come in groups to sporting events. Reysen and Branscombe (2010) explained that sport tourists tend to spend their resources to obtain goods and services pertaining to their team. Decision-makers such as sport marketers, city planners, and politicians will be interested in knowing how to increase the sport tourists' revisit intention because of the benefits sport tourists bring in. Thus, this study offers a framework to understand how sport nostalgia influences the revisit intention of sport tourists taking into account the role of emotions and positive electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM).

As far as sport tourism is concerned, Cho et al. (2014) highlighted the need for more research on how sport nostalgia influences sport tourists' behaviour. Research is scarce regarding how nostalgia affects the travel behaviour of sport tourists (e.g., Fairley, 2003; Fairley et al., 2018). As such, this study presents a conceptual framework to investigate the influence of sport nostalgia on revisit intention. To better understand the relationship, discrete positive emotions and positive eWOM are also

considered. The authors argue that this framework will be of immense value to sport marketers and managers.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Sport Nostalgia

Negative connotations such as homesickness and nostalgia are considered to be related (Hofer, 1934). The term nostalgia is gradually considered to be positive and newer meanings are associated with the term. Only selective memories trigger nostalgia and positive memories are only counted toward it. Stern (1992) emphasized that nostalgia is "an emotional state in which an individual yearns for an idealized or sanitized version of an earlier time period" (p.11). According to Davis (1979), negative sentiments and nostalgic feelings are not related. Sport nostalgia, past experiences, and future behaviour are closely related (Cho et al., 2014; Cho et al., 2019; Fairley et al., 2018). Memories of individuals significantly play a role in developing sport nostalgia (Cho et al., 2014), and volunteers of sporting events can become nostalgic toward the events, not just the spectators and participants (Fairley et al., 2007). Sporting events can help develop experiences that can fall into one of the different types of sport nostalgia (i.e.) spectating or volunteering experiences.

When individuals visit historic sporting sites and feel nostalgic towards favorite teams or past athletes, then those individuals are experiencing object-based sport nostalgia (Gibson et al., 2002). Alternatively, when individuals feel nostalgic by cherishing their memories of socializing with others and when they seek the same experiences in the sporting occasions, then those individuals are experiencing experience-based sport nostalgia (Fairley, 2003). Sport-related objects such as place, artifact, and a person can evoke sport nostalgia. On the other hand, when individuals learn experiences from family and friends, these experiences can also evoke sport nostalgia (Meyer, 2010).

Sport nostalgia can take on one of the following forms: a) experience, b) socialization, c) personal identity, and d) group identity (Cho et al., 2014). Sport nostalgia can take on the experience form when the memories of attractions and environments (i.e., when fans see their favorite athlete playing, or when fans hear an iconic sound) play a role in eliciting nostalgic feelings (Snyder, 1991; Fairley & Gammon, 2005; Gordon, 2013; Gammon, 2015). Sport nostalgia can take on the socialization form when individuals' longing for a close relationship with others in the past sporting events play a role in eliciting nostalgic feelings. Lastly, sport nostalgia can take on the personal identity or group identity form when the past experiences that make them feel valued as an independent person or a member of a group play a role in eliciting nostalgic feelings. Cho et al. (2017) developed the Nostalgia Scale for Sport

Tourism (NSST) that contains five dimensions: sport team, environment, socialization, personal identity, and group identity and features 29 items. Research is sparse regarding the relationship between each dimension of sport nostalgia and other constructs in influencing the sport tourists' revisit intention.

2.2 Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) Model

In our study, the Stimuli-Organism-Response (SOR) model was used as its theoretical underpinning. Mehrabian and Russell (1974) invented the SOR model, in which environment stimulus (S) leads to emotional response (O), which results in behavioural response (R). Various scholars have articulated its importance in retail settings such as the tendency of customers to buy impulsively (Chang et al., 2013), and decisions of customers to engage in buying behaviour (Lucia-Palacios et al., 2016). In the marketing literature, SOR-based research works establish the linkage between emotional response and the tendency of customers to engage in purchase behaviour, their intentions, and their tendency to return (Li et al., 2011; Choi et al., 2011).

This model has also been applied to understand an individual's behaviour in sporting events (Uhrich & Benkenstein, 2010). For instance, music played during the events or foods sold and sporting venues' appearance serve as stimuli to sport tourists. In our study, such stimuli could lead to sport nostalgia, which is an emotional state that results in behavioural responses. On other sporting occasions as well, similar relations have been reported between sport nostalgia and intentions (e.g., Kulczycki & Hyatt, 2005, Fairley et al., 2018; Fairley, 2003). Diverse stimuli in sporting events affect individuals' memories, attitudes, and behaviour (Krishna, 2012). Besides the SOR model, empirical studies indicate that there exists a positive relationship between nostalgia and behaviour (Kim et al., 2019; Sierra & McQuitty, 2007). As far as sport tourism is concerned, research by Gibson et al. (2002) indicated that college football could lead to sport nostalgia which resulted in their participation in sporting events. In the context of sport tourism, only very few studies have explored the causal relationship between nostalgia and attitude. Previous studies in other settings have established a positive relationship between them (e.g., Shimp, 1981; Pascal et al., 2002; Ju et al., 2017). Nostalgia and attitude are distinct but related concepts, as past experiences regarding people dictate both nostalgia and attitude (Cho et al., 2014; Baker & Kennedy, 1994).

2.3 Emotional Experiences

Academics and practitioners agree on the importance of the role of emotions in comprehending consumption experiences and behaviour (Mattila & Enz, 2002; Han & Jeong, 2013). Emotions influence satisfaction, word-of-mouth (WOM), and loyalty by playing the role of markers, mediators, and moderators (Joireman et al., 2013; Bagozzi

et al., 1999; Han & Jeong, 2013). Individuals pursue emotions and experiences by travelling. When individuals return home, they retain those emotions and experiences in their minds. In tourism, service experience evaluation is particularly emotional.

This paper attempts to significantly contribute to sport tourism research by examining the role of positive emotional experiences on eWOM and the behavioural intentions of sport tourists. With competition becoming more and more intense, policymakers are aware that experiences are difficult to copy. They are aware that simple commodities are not of much value and they are trying to promote unique experiences. Policy makers want to use emotional experiences as a differentiation element to increase positive eWOM. Using emotional experiences could become a source of competitive advantage.

Researchers have started giving importance to understand the role of emotions in tourism research (Gnoth, 1997; Goossens, 2000). Previous research focused on understanding the role of emotional experiences in shopping, restaurants, theme parks, holidays, and festivals context (Lee et al., 2008; del Bosque & San Martín, 2008), but research is scarce that focuses on the role of emotions in the context of sport tourism.

Research shows that tourist emotional reactions influence post-consumption behaviours. Research by Yuksel and Yuksel (2007), Bigné et al. (2005), and Grappi and Montanari (2011) analyzed the impact of emotions on satisfaction and behavioural intentions. Tourism research asserts that emotions play a significant role. The relationship among emotions, satisfaction and behavioural intentions is difficult to comprehend (Bigné et al., 2005).

2.4 Electronic Word-of-Mouth (eWOM)

Word-of-mouth (WOM) recommendations heavily influence consumer attitudes and purchase intentions. Research indicates that compared to marketer-controlled information sources, WOM referrals are more influential (Buttle, 1998). When customers hear recommendations from trustworthy sources, they consider that to be more objective, compared to the information they hear from traditional advertising sources (Trusov et al., 2009). Electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) has gained traction because of digital channels and social media. Consumers view WOM recommendations as very important sources of information in their decision-making process, especially in the hospitality and tourism industry (Litvin et al., 2008). Since eWOM is playing an influential role, scholars have started giving importance to analyse its impact on attitudes and decision-making. In general, eWOM is of fundamental importance within sports tourism. Since the emergence of eWOM, new research questions are being analysed. For instance, are the relationships established between WOM and other constructs hold when we consider eWOM? Since eWOM is widely prevalent, this paper

tries to establish the links between different constructs in the context of sport tourism. Some researchers (Vermuelen & Seegers, 2009; Litvin et al., 2008; Filieri & McLeay, 2014) have pointed out that more research is needed to explore the behavioural implications of eWOM on travelers. Also, the impact of positive discrete emotions on eWOM generation needs to be better understood.

2.5 Revisit Intention

Revisit Intention indicates the readiness of individuals to visit the destination or the site that they visited before (Cole & Scott, 2004). If marketers are successful in bringing previous visitors to the destination, it is much more profitable (Chi, 2012; Um et al., 2006), and re-visitors will spend more money and engage in positive WOM (Marinkovic et al., 2014). Even for sporting events, these behaviours hold. Sporting events can be a huge success economically if marketing managers manage to bring back sport tourists for future events (Chalip & McGuirty, 2004). Because of this reason, revisit intention is often studied in sport tourism research. Revisit intention and intention to recommend are the widely examined types of behavioural intentions.

In previous research, predicting variables influence revisit intention, which is the outcome variable. In most studies, travel satisfaction directly influences revisit intention. When visitors are not satisfied, they do not like to return to the place they visited before (e.g., Guntoro & Hui, 2013). More than overall satisfaction, the perceived attractiveness of a destination is found to be a significant predictor of revisit intention (Um et al., 2006).

Research indicates that perceived value, travel motivation, and destination image are the other predictors of revisit intention (Chang et al., 2014; Um et al., 2006; Leong et al., 2015; Stylos et al., 2016).

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Previous research indicates that nostalgia favors positive memories and emotions and mitigates negative feelings (Davis, 1979). Other scholars, such as Peters (1985) state that nostalgia features "as madness mingled with yearning" (p.136). Nostalgia comprises both positive and negative emotional valence and it is a multifaceted feeling (Johnson-Laird & Oatley, 1989; Dickinson & Erben, 2006; Batcho, 2007; Barrett et al., 2010). To examine how emotions change for both personal and historical nostalgia in the advertising context, Marchegiani and Phau (2013) utilize a 57- emotion profile. Based on the similarity of the characteristics (Ekman, 1992), they compress the most important emotions into the following five discrete emotion families: negative/irritation, upbeat/elation, loss/regret, serenity/calm, and warm/tender.

Though nostalgia comprises different emotions, positive emotions take precedence over negative emotions since individuals long for the past (Holak & Havlena, 1998; Zhou et al., 2008; Cheung et al., 2013). In our study, we predict the negative emotions to play a minor role since the study focuses on sport tourists in the context of sport tourism. Consistent with prior research by Li et al. (2019), the two negative emotion groups (i.e., loss/regret, negative/irritation) from the five discrete emotion families are not included in this study. When individuals do not have access to what was available in the past (Hunt & Johns, 2013; Zhou et al., 2012a), nostalgia maintains physiological comfort. Nostalgia temporally fills the void (Valis, 2000) and increases an individual's relationship with other people (Lasaleta et al., 2014). When the void is filled, individuals' affective response is positive and elated emotions come into picture (Wildschut et al., 2006). If the packaging design is nostalgic, it was found to elicit the emotions of upbeat/elation, serenity/calm, and, warm/tender (Chen, 2014). Thus, the following hypotheses were proposed.

- H1: Sport Nostalgia and Upbeat/Elation emotion are positively related.
- H2: Sport Nostalgia and Serenity/Calm emotion are positively related.
- H3: Sport Nostalgia and Warm/Tender emotion are positively related.

Previous research confirms that there exists a relationship between positive emotions and WOM (Ladhari, 2007), and willingness to recommend (Jang & Namkung, 2009; Lee et al., 2008), though not in the sport tourism context. In the sport tourism context, positive emotions could create value through positive recommendations. The positive emotions could also create revenue in sport tourism. Academy and industry have paid great attention to the topic of eWOM, but research is scarce that addresses the factors that influence eWOM intentions (Yang, 2017).

Substantial cross-sectional research has been done on the relationship between emotions and customer behavioural intentions. There search vehemently supports a valence congruent relationship (Yu & Dean, 2001; White, 2006; Nyer, 1997; Dube & Menon, 2000; Ladhari, 2007; Westbrook, 1987). Individuals who score highly on a cluster of emotions labeled calm/tolerant tend to perceive the service provision favorably and the chances that they will engage in negative WOM behaviour are less. Conversely, if the consumers score highly on a hostile / angry cluster, they will engage in different kinds of behaviour (Maute & Dube, 1999). Individuals tend to share their emotional experiences with others (Kramer et al., 2014). Thus, the following hypotheses were proposed.

- H4: Upbeat/Elation emotion is positively related to Positive eWOM.
- H5: Serenity/Calm emotion is positively related to Positive eWOM.
- H6: Warm/Tender emotion is positively related to Positive eWOM.

Intention to revisit indicates the readiness of consumers to visit a destination again. The cost of attracting new visitors is more than the cost of retaining re-visitors (Um et al., 2006). Destination marketers are showing much interest in understanding what drives tourists to revisit. Because of eWOM communication's huge impact on marketing strategy, it has received huge attention in recent years (Smith et al., 2007). Gretzel and Yoo (2008) further found that when other travelers provide reviews, readers perceive them to be enjoyable, reliable, and more up-to-date than the information provided by travel service providers. More specifically, in the hotel and travel industry, empirical evidence suggested that eWOM significantly influences tourists' revisit intention (e.g., Arsal et al., 2008; Ye et al., 2009; Vermeulen & Seegers, 2009; Filieri, 2015; Filieri & McLeay, 2014; Sparks & Browning, 2011). This study contends that in the sport tourism industry, positive eWOM should have a strong positive influence on revisit intention. If the positive eWOM is present, then there will be an increase in the intention of sport tourists to revisit a place, while the negative eWOM will diminish the chances of sport tourists to revisit a place. Previous research indicates that eWOM communication has a positive impact on tourist travel intentions and their attitude to return (Albarq, 2013; Lee et al., 2009; Lee & Cranage, 2014; Sparks & Browning, 2011). Thus, the following hypothesis was proposed.

H7: Positive eWOM is positively related to Revisit Intention.

When individuals incur nostalgic feelings, their behaviour will be in such a way that it tends to allay their longing for the past (Schindler & Holbrook, 2003, Cho et al., 2019; Cho et al., 2020). According to Ali (2015) and Chen and Chen (2010), in heritage tourism settings, tourists tend to develop feelings of nostalgia toward past tourism experiences, if those experiences are satisfactory to them. These nostalgic feelings can increase their intention to revisit. Personal nostalgia significantly influenced travel attitude and intention (Phau et al., 2016). Similarly, to resolve their nostalgic desire, sport tourists could revisit sporting events that manifest positive memories of the past. For example, Fairley (2003) found that if sport fans recollect nostalgic past group experiences, their revisit intention increases. Also, Gammon and Ramshaw (2005) found that if feelings of nostalgia can be triggered among sport tourists, it will result in sport tourists visiting iconic sport-related attractions. Thus, the following hypothesis was proposed.

H8: Sport Nostalgia and Revisit Intention are positively related.

Figure 1. Proposed Conceptual Model

4. THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

This conceptual study makes several theoretical contributions. It establishes a conceptual model that connects sport nostalgia, discrete positive emotions, positive eWOM, and revisit intention in the sport tourism context. This study connects sport nostalgia with revisit intention via discrete positive emotions and positive eWOM. Specifically, this model predicts that sport nostalgia positively impacts upbeat/elation, serenity/calm, warm/tender emotions. It also supports a positive relationship between the discrete positive emotions and positive eWOM. Finally, the overall proposed model demonstrates how the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) model works in sport nostalgia. This theory describes that environment stimulus(S) leads to emotional response (O), which results in behavioural response (R). In our study, the stimuli provided could lead to sport nostalgia, which in turn influences revisit intention. The proposed model suggests that sport tourists' revisit intention could be encouraged when they feel sport nostalgia. When they feel sport nostalgia, it has an effect on discrete positive emotions, which affects positive eWOM, which in turn positively influences revisit intention.

5. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

For practitioners, the proposed conceptual model underscores the importance of inducing sport nostalgia to increase sport tourists' revisit intention. The important task for the sport marketers and policymakers is to provide meaningful and pleasant experiences, which induces sport nostalgia. When sport tourists complete their maiden visit, sport marketers could send re-collective messages and try to make the experiences or memories more glamorous. To increase the revisit intention, sport marketing managers need to evoke positive emotions such as upbeat/elation, serenity/calm, and warm/tender by providing sport tourists with fond memories that remind them of the "good old days." Positive eWOM is extremely important in the sport tourism context.

Therefore, sport marketers should look for ways to increase the positive comments. This study suggests that if managers provide emotional experiences to sport tourists, it will enhance the likelihood of positive comments through the various online platforms. If sport marketers can properly manage emotional experiences, and positive reviews are generated, it will help them to increase the sport tourists' revisit intention.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Although there are many theoretical and practical implications, future research studies should expand upon this work. The hypotheses proposed in this study should be empirically tested. During empirical testing, multiple items could be used to measure each construct. For example, sport nostalgia can be measured with the Nostalgia Scale for Sport Tourism (NSST) developed by Cho et al. (2017) which contains 29 items across the five dimensions of sport team, environment, socialization, personal identity, and group identity. SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) can be used to empirically test the model since there are multiple latent variables. Cultural factors may play a role in influencing sport tourists' thinking and behaviour. Certain sports are popular in certain countries (e.g., football in the United States or cricket in India). As such, the relationship between sport nostalgia, discrete positive emotions, positive eWOM, and revisit intention will be different in different countries. Further research should focus on different countries and different sports. Although the current study has several limitations, it sheds light on how sport nostalgia could be used beneficially in the sport tourism context.

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